

A STUDY ON THE TACTILE SENSING SYSTEM USING PIEZOELECTRIC FIBER

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1 Introduction

Currently, the researches on developing flexible tactile sensors for the artificial skins have been actively.[1-9]. In particular piezoelectric, optic or chemical sensor have been used by being inserted in pliable materials such as silicones, polyesters and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) for flexible tactile sensors.[10-14].

Recently, fiber or strip-type piezoelectric polymers became the appropriate sensing materials for tactile sensors due to their excellent flexibility, but related studies for the multi-axial load detection are still in an early stage. For this reason, basic parametric studies such as types, shapes and embedded locations of piezoelectric polymers should be preceded under multi-axial loads.

Accordingly, this study developed the tactile sensor made by PVDF strip embedded PDMS to have flexibility, and investigated the sensing performance through measuring the signals generated from tactile sensors under the multi-axial forces.

In particular, this study focuses on effects of arrangement of embedded piezoelectric polymer films in order to separate measured signals against each multi-axial load.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Piezoelectric Characteristics

The piezoelectric characteristics of the piezoelectric film used in this study use the interaction between mechanical and electric energy, referring to the

characteristic that the film undergo the electric dipole changes when external forces are applied.

Piezoelectric properties can be classified as the piezoelectric strain e (C/m²) and stress piezoelectric constant d (C/N) as shown in Equation (1) and (2).

$$d = \left[\frac{\partial a}{\partial \sigma} \right]_b = \left[\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial b} \right]_{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

$$e = \left[\frac{\partial a}{\partial \varepsilon} \right]_b = \left[\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial b} \right]_{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

where σ , ε , a , b , d , e represent stress (Pa), strain (m/m), electric flux density (C/m²), electric field (V/m), and two piezoelectric constants, respectively. This study intends to conduct a basic research on developing multi-axial force sensor by analyzing characteristics of electric signals under external loads.

2.2 Materials and Specimens

Specimens have a structure similar to composite materials. The piezoelectric film is used to measure multi-axial forces similar to the reinforce materials of composite materials and PDMS was used to protect sensors and give flexibility to the tactile sensor similar to the matrix material. Product information and mechanical properties of PVDF film and PDMS are shown in Table 1.

Three continuous-type specimens with vertically arrayed (Fig. 1a), horizontally arrayed (Fig. 1b) and crosswise arrayed (Fig. 1c) PVDF films, and one discontinuous-type specimen (Fig. 1d) are fabricated

Table 1. Specification of PVDF Film and matrix materials.

		Sensor	Skin
Manufacturer		Kureha	Daw corning
Product Name		PVDF Film 80 μm	Sylgard 184
Piezoelectric constant	d_{31}	22 pC / N	-
	d_{32}	2 pC / N	
	d_{33}	35 pC / N	
	e_{31}	75 mC / m^2	
	e_{32}	6 mC / m^2	
	e_{33}	105 mC / m^2	
Tensile Modulus (MPa)		3000	0.36~0.87
Tensile Strength (MPa)		11.7~14.1	2.24

Fig. 2. Manufacturing process of Piezoelectric sensor embedded specimens: (a) Fabrication of electrodes on PVDF films, (b) Installation of PVDF films between upper and lower molds, (c) Mold assembly and matrix injection.

to figure out sensing with respect to the arrangement of piezoelectric polymer films as shown in Fig. 1. Manufacturing process of specimens is shown in Fig. 2. First, the film was cut silver pastes were coated on the upper and lower surfaces of films and the two ends of the film are connected to electric wires to measure the piezo-electric properties. Then prepared PVDF films were installed between upper and lower molds and matrix materials are put inside the mold. Specimens were cured at 80 degrees for 2 hours.

2.3 Experimentals

The testing machine shown in Fig. 3. was used to measure the sensing performance of developed tactile sensors under multi-axis forces. This testing machine is internally made equipped for this study in order to apply vertical forces using electro-dynamic actuator and the horizontal forces (like frictional forces) by moving the basement with specimens using a linear motor.

Specification of important components for the testing equipment are shown in Table. 2.

For the mono-axial loading experiments, a voice coil motor attached on the top of the testing machine was used to apply sinusoidal forces to the specimen, taking the magnitude, location and speed of the input load, and PVDF film arrangements as test variables.

Fig. 1. Configuration of three continuous-type specimens with vertically arrayed (a), horizontally arrayed (b) and crosswise arrayed (c) PVDF films, and one discontinuous-type specimen (d).

Fig. 3. Photographs of testing equipment

Fig. 4 shows the representative graph of applied load and measured electric signals under the vertical force only. As seen in Fig. 4 depending on the input load in the form of sine waveform, measured electric signals from the film show similar tendency to the input load with the sine waveform.

Table 2. Specification of important components for the testing equipment.

Linear motor	Product name	LA-3
	manufacturer	TGG
	specifications	Speed : 4~40mm/s Load : 50~1200N
Linear rail / Roller	Product name	PLR2C / BJKR
	manufacturer	MISUMI
	specifications	-
Load cell	Product name	CBFSA / LF 1
	manufacturer	CAS Korea / KOZY International
	specifications	Load : 300 / 200N
Voice coil motor	Product name	-
	manufacturer	-
	specifications	Load : 100N Displacement : ± 30mm
Displacement sensor	Product name	OD Value
	manufacturer	RADIAN
	specifications	Displacement : 60~180mm

The result of the mono-axial loading experiments was analyzed by comparing the maximum and minimum values of the applied loads and the electric signals.

For the multi-axial loading experiments, static vertical forces are applied to the specimen using a weight pendulum and dynamic horizontal forces are introduced using a linear motor. The experiment variables included the magnitude of the vertical forces, the speed of the horizontal forces, and PVDF film arrangements.

Fig. 5 shows representative graph of applied loads and measured electric signals under the multi-axial forces. When the linear motor moves at a constant

Fig. 4. Representative graph of applied loads and measured electric signals under the vertical load only

Fig. 5. Representative graph of applied loads and measured electric signals under the multi-axial forces.

speed, the location of the vertical loading tip changes, and the maximum electric signals were observed when the vertical loading tip passes above the film. Then the maximum electric signal values are analyzed with respect to the experimental.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mono-axial Loading Experiments

The following are selected experiment variables for mono-axial loading experiments. Different input loads were applied such as 15, 25, 35 and 45N to check electric signal changes with respect to the magnitude of the vertical load. For investigating the effect of the loading position, vertical loads were applied to the positions designated by circled number depending on each array as shown in Fig. 6. To evaluate the effect of the loading speed, the frequency of the sinusoidal load was changed from 1 to 5, 10 and 20Hz.

Fig. 7 shows characteristics of electric signals changing depending on three different array types when the load was applied on the position ① of all specimens. It was commonly observed that the higher the load became, the more linear the resulting electric signal values were. The discontinuous-type specimen shows lower signal than the continuous-type specimen because the relatively smaller amount of sensors (PVDF films) was inserted in the matrix. And the signal measured on the vertical line of the continuous-type specimens with crosswise arrayed PVDF films was higher than those with vertically arrayed PVDF films because the load applied to the former is closer to the load applied and more deformed.

Fig. 8 shows measured electric signals with respect to the distance between the loading and sensing positions. Vertical force of 10N was applied on the position ①~⑤ as shown in Fig. 6. When the loading position was ① (right on the sensing PVDF film), measured electric signals were much higher than

others. However, if the distance was over 10mm, the signal started to dramatically drop.

(c)

(d)

Fig. 6. Dimensions and loading positions of specimens with (a) vertically arrayed continuous, (b) horizontally arrayed continuous, (c) crosswise arrayed discontinuous, and (d) crosswise arrayed continuous PVDF films.

Fig. 9 represents measured electrical signals with respect to the speed of applied mono-axial vertical loads. The experiment was done under the constant vertical force of 10N applied on the position ① as shown in Fig. 6 with the frequency of 1, 5, 10 and 20Hz. As shown in Fig. 9 measured electric signals of each specimen were almost same regardless of the

Fig. 7. Measured electric signals with respect to the magnitude of applied mono-axial vertical loads

Fig. 8. Measured electric signals with respect to the distance between the loading and sensing position under the monoaxial vertical loads

Fig. 9. Measured electric signals with respect to the speed of applied monoaxial vertical loads

loading speed.

3.2 Multi-axial Loading Experiments

In order to apply the multi-axial loading, specimens were moved horizontally under the vertical forces. Due to the friction between loading bar and specimens, the developed tactile sensor receives undergoes both of vertical and horizontal forces simultaneously.

Multi-axial loading experiments were done on the continuous-type specimen with crosswise arrayed PVDF films as shown in Fig. 10 The experimental parameters were horizontal forces and horizontally moving speeds.

The graph in Fig. 11 shows characteristics of the electric signal measured with respect to the horizontal forces under the multi-axial loads and the horizontally moving speed of 10mm/s. The result confirmed that the higher the horizontal force was, the higher the signal gets.

Fig. 10. Configuration of multi-axial loading experiments.

The graph in Fig. 12 shows characteristics of the electric signal measured with respect to the horizontally moving speed under the horizontal force of 10N. The result confirmed that the higher the horizontally moving speed was, the higher the signal gets.

Fig. 11. Measured electric signals with respect to the horizontal forces under the multi-axial loads

Fig. 12. Measured electric signals with respect to the horizontally moving speeds under the multi-axial loads

4. Conclusion

This study analyzed characteristics of electric signal changes depending on the arrangement types of the embedded piezoelectric polymer sensor under external multi-axial forces.

Three continuous-type specimens with vertically arrayed (Fig. 1a), horizontally arrayed (Fig. 1b) and crosswise arrayed (Fig. 1c) PVDF films, and one discontinuous-type specimen are fabricated to figure out sensing with respect to the arrangement of piezoelectric polymer films. It was found that as the load increases, the electric signal values increases more for the continuous type than the discontinuous type. In proportion to the amount of the film sensor included in the specimen, the signal was measured higher for the continuous type than the discontinuous type under the same load.

Depending on the magnitude of the load, regardless of the arrangement types, the higher the load was applied, the higher the signal was measured in a linear form.

Based on this result, it is presumed that the arrangement types of embedded piezoelectric polymer films, and magnitude and location of the load can be found through analysis of characteristics of the electric signal.

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References

- [1] J.H.KIM, J.I.LEE, Y.K.PARK, M.S.KIM and D.I.KANG “Development of tactile sensor and its application”. *Korean Society of Precision Engineering*, 21, 1999.
- [2] H.Y.HWANG “Piezoelectric particle reinforced polyurethane for tactile sensing robot skin”. *Mechanics for composite materials*, Vol. 47, No.1, 2011
- [3] K.H.YU, M.J.YOON, G.Y.JEONG, T.G.KWON, S.C.LEE “Development of distributed flexible tactile sensor system”. *Journal of the Korean Society of Precision Engineering*, Vol. 19, No. 1, January 2002.
- [4] H.Y.HWANG “Piezoelectric particle reinforced polyurethane for tactile sensing robot skin”. *Mechanics for composite materials*, Vol. 47, No.1, 2011
- [5] Y.H.YUN, S.J.KIM, Y.C.LEE, K.H.YU, S.C.LEE “Characteristic evaluation of PVDF tactile sensor”. *Korean Society for Precision Engineering*, 1999.
- [6] K.H.YU, M.J.YOON, T.G.KWON, S.C.LEE H.Y. Hwang “Fabrication and characteristic evaluation of a flexible tactile sensor using PVDF”. *Journal of the Korean Society of Precision Engineering*, Vol. 18, No.7, January 2001
- [7] G.D.MARIA, C.NATALE, S.PIROZZI “Force / tactile sensor for robotic applications”. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, Vol. 175, 2012.
- [8] L.SEMINARA, M.CAPURRO, P.CIRILLO, G.CANNATA, M.VALLE “Electromechanical characterization of piezoelectric PVDF polymer films for tactile sensors in robotics applications”. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, Vol. 169, September 2011.
- [9] Y.TANAKA, M.TANAKA, S.CHONAN “Measurement and valuation of tactile warmth using a PVDF Sensor”. *International Journal of Applied Electromagnetics and Mechanics*, Vol. 23, 2006
- [10] G.N.KIM, Y.G.KIM, Y.K.LEE, W.S.JO, D.S.LEE, G.N. JO, “Development of silicon based flexible tactile sensor array mounted on flexible PCB”, *Japan Society for Simulation Technology*. Vol. 15, No 4, 2006
- [11] J.S.HEO, J.H.CHUNG, J.J.LEE “Tactile sensor arrays using fiber Bragg grating sensors” *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*. Vol. 126, No.2, 14 February 2006
- [12] A. DAMORE, G.D.MARIA, L. GRASSIA, C. NATALE, S. PIROZZI “Silicone-rubber-based tactile sensors for the measurement of normal and tangential components of the contact force” *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*. Vol. 122, No 6, August 2011
- [13] M. SHIMOJO, A. NAMIKI, M. ISHIKAWA, R.MAKINO “A tactile sensor sheet using pressure conductive rubber whit electrical – wires stitched method” *Sensors Journal IEEE*, Vol. 4, No 5. October 2004
- [14] S.K.HWANG, H.Y.HWANG. “The effect of the electrode arrangement on the piezoelectric

monitoring for the robot skins,” *Proceedings of 2011
Spring Conference of KSME, Jeju, Korea, 2011*